

LEASING RELATIONS IN SMALL BUSINESS ENTITIES

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Annotation: This article devoted to enhance the awareness of leasing (and its importance) as additional financing technique for SMEs that expands the access to short- and medium-term financing for capital equipment. In addition to this resent data and researches related to topic were analyzed.

Key words: *external financing , asymmetric information, lessor, collateral, Conventional bank, track record, hire-purchase.*

It is well known that Micro and Small and Medium sized Enterprises (SMEs) are the backbone of the economy. Most of these companies use external financing sources like debt and equity capital to finance their activities. However, in general, in the area of SMEs' access to finance, there are market imperfections - not only in times of crisis, but on an on-going basis as a fundamental structural issue, based on uncertainty and asymmetric information between the demand side (entrepreneur) and the supply side (financial intermediary).

Leasing is a possibility for SMEs to expand their access to short- and medium-term financing. From an economic perspective, leasing can be defined as “a contract between two parties where one party (the lessor) provides an asset for usage to another party (the lessee) for a specified period of time, in return for specified payments”[1]. This is also reflected in accounting-related definitions: According to the Accounting Standard IAS 17 “a lease is an agreement whereby the lessor conveys to the lessee in return for a payment or series of payments the right to use an asset for an agreed period of time”. Leasing is referred to as asset based financing. As lessors retain ownership of the assets they lease throughout the life of the contract, these leased assets are therefore an inherent form of collateral in such contracts (compared to traditional bank lending which will either be unsecured or make use of different types of collateral and typically not physical assets such as equipment which are inherent in leases). Conventional bank lending focuses on the loan repayment by the borrower from two sources: a

primary source, the cash flow generation, and a secondary source, credit enhancements and collateral (if any). Leasing is focused on the lessee's ability to generate cash flows from the business operations to service the lease payments, as the lessor retains legal ownership of the asset. Hence, leasing separates the legal ownership of an asset from its economic use. Ownership of the asset may or may not pass to the customer at the end of the lease contract. Contracts, where legal ownership of the asset passes directly to the customer at the start of the agreement, are not considered to be leases.

Based on contractual arrangements, the lessee is allowed to use an asset which is owned by the lessor; the lessee pays specified periodic rentals (see figure 1). The lessor relies on the lessee's ability to generate sufficient cash flows to pay the lease rentals (rather than to rely on the lessee's other assets or track record/credit history). Leasing enables also borrowers with limited track record / credit histories and collateral to access the use of capital equipment, often even in cases where they would not qualify for traditional commercial bank lending[2]. Organisationally and technically, leasing companies have to be able to assess the value of the physical assets being leased in order to sell on the secondary market, or lease again the assets that have not been eventually purchased by their customers.

In many statistics, leasing is combined with hire-purchase and factoring. The term hire-purchase covers different types of contracts from country to country. In some cases, hire purchase involves the transfer of ownership of the asset at the end of the contract, either automatically or through the exercise of a purchase option. These types of hire purchase contracts are therefore leases (i.e. in the UK, Germany, Poland and the Netherlands). However, in cases where ownership transfers at the beginning of the contract, these types of contracts are closer to an instalment credit contract than a lease. Factoring is typically an arrangement under which a financial intermediary (the factor) collects the debts of its client in return for a service charge in the form of discount or rebate (or to describe it the other way round: the company sells its receivables to the factor at a discount). The factor eliminates the company's risk of bad debts by taking over the responsibility of book debts due to the client. Leasing is often seen as substitute for medium to long term credit, but the answer to the question whether leasing and debt are substitutes or complements is not trivial and has in financial literature not resulted in a clear conclusion[3]. In traditional corporate finance the decision of buying versus leasing is mostly discussed in the context of the Modigliani and Miller (1958) world of perfect capital markets (where in general the capital structure is irrelevant for the determination of the firm value). But in real financial markets, there are market imperfections. In the area of access to

finance for SMEs, a market imperfection/failure is not only present during a deep recession or a financial crisis but also on an on-going basis as a fundamental structural issue. The reasons for a market failure relate to insufficient supply of capital (debt or equity) and inadequacies on the demand side. This market failure is mainly based on asymmetric information (in the case of debt: information gap between lender and borrower), combined with uncertainty, which causes agency problems that affect debt providers' behaviour. Hence, leasing is an alternative mechanism to facilitate access to finance; it enables the use of capital equipment in particular for new/young enterprises without credit track record and with limited possibilities to provide collateral. This refers especially to situations of (from the bankers' perspective rational but) de facto unjustified credit rationing: the real creditworthiness of the SME can be better than the perceived quality (i.e. if a financial institution's decision to lend is based on collateral and track record, rather than the economic viability of the business). Consequently, leasing is also a tool to mitigate market weaknesses in SME lending. That this is the case is also shown by the fact that there is no adverse selection process (adverse selection would mean that by trend the companies with the highest (real) credit risk would lease because they do not receive the respective loans).

Adverse selection would result in high default rates in the leasing business. However, one could also argue that these rates are low in particular among SMEs, because the leased equipment is typically too important to the lessees' operations to lose it by defaulting on lease payments. Empirical results show indeed that leasing exposures are associated with relatively low risk compared to other forms of financing. "The presence of physical collaterals no doubt contributes very largely to this reduced risk profile"[4].¹¹ Overall, academic literature underlines the advantages of leasing as an additional financing form for enterprises. Leasing is an alternative mechanism to facilitate access to finance, even more in the current market environment (e.g. current efforts to change financial market regulations, in particular Basel III liquidity provisions, might hamper long-term SME loan financing (e.g. ACCA, 2012)). Leasing can serve as a helpful financing tool for SMEs which provides financing close to the investment periods of the leased assets. Public support of this instrument can help to mitigate market weaknesses and to enhance the access to finance for SMEs. SMEs finance themselves to a great extent by internal sources, both from the business owner and through retained profit. Many SMEs also use external sources of finance, informal sources (such as family and friends, and some types of business angel investment) and formal sources, such as bank loans, leasing, trade credits, factoring and more "formal" Venture Capital, which is important for a select group of

high potential SMEs (EIM, 2009). Nevertheless, as mentioned above, SMEs have usually more difficulties in accessing external financing than large enterprises.

To sum up all given facts above it should be noted that , SMEs expect leasing to stay of high relevance as integral part of their financing tool set. However, the supply side has come under extraordinary pressure in the current economic and financial crisis. Thus, public support not only helps to enhance the access to finance for SMEs in general, but also to counteract the severe impact of the financial crisis on refinancing conditions and the implied consequences for investment and growth.

REFERENCES:

1. Fletcher, M.; Freeman, R.; Sultanov, M. and Umarov, U. (2005). Leasing in development. Guidelines for emerging economies. IFC. 2005.
2. Gallardo, J. (1997). Leasing to support small businesses and microenterprises. In: The World Bank. Policy Research Working Paper 1857. December 1997.
3. Severin, E and Filareto-Deghaye, M.-C. (2007). Determinants of the choice leasing vs bank loan: evidence form the French SME by KACM. In: Revista Investigación Operacional Vol. 28 No. 2 120- 130, 2007.
4. Schmit, M. (2005). Is Automotive Leasing a Risky Business? In: Revue de l'association française de finance. Vol 26. No. 2/2005, pp. 35-66.